

Supplemental Materials

for

“Two Decades of Embodied CO₂ in MENA’s Construction Sector: Regional Insights and Policy Implications”

S1. Complete EE-MRIO Derivation and Construction Sector Isolation

S1.1 Full Mathematical Derivation of the EE-MRIO Framework

To complement the concise presentation in the main manuscript, we provide the complete mathematical derivation of the EE-MRIO framework. The fundamental input-output identity begins with the disaggregated representation of sectoral outputs:

$$x_i^r = \sum_{s=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m z_{ij}^{rs} + \sum_{s=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^q y_i^{rs} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where:

- x_i^r : Total economic output of sector i in region r
- z_{ij}^{rs} : Intermediate use of sector j in region s produced by sector i in region r
- y_i^{rs} : Final demand in region s from sector i in region r

Defining the technical coefficients as $a_{ij}^{rs} = z_{ij}^{rs}/x_j^s$ and using vector/matrix notation with $\mathbf{x} = [x_j^s]_{NR \times 1}$, $\mathbf{y} = [y_i^{rs}]_{NR \times 1}$, and $\mathbf{A} = [a_{ij}^{rs}]_{NR \times NR}$, the system can be expressed in compact matrix form as Equations (1)–(3) in the main text.

The Leontief inverse $\mathbf{L} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}$ can be expanded as a power series:

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^2 + \mathbf{A}^3 + \dots \quad (\text{S2})$$

This expansion demonstrates how the inverse captures both direct (\mathbf{I}) and indirect ($\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^2 + \dots$) requirements throughout the supply chain.

S1.2 Construction Final Demand Selector Matrix \mathbf{M}

To isolate the embodied emissions driven specifically by the construction sector’s final demand, we constructed a selector matrix \mathbf{M} . Let the final demand vector $\mathbf{y}_{\text{total}}$ have dimensions $[NR \times 1]$, where N is the number of sectors (26) and R is the total number of regions in the Eora26 database (189 regions, including our 23 MENA countries plus Rest of World).

The matrix \mathbf{M} is a diagonal matrix of the same dimension as $\mathbf{y}_{\text{total}}$, where the elements corresponding to the row indices of the ‘Construction’ sector (Eora26 sector code: **CNS**) for all 23 MENA countries are set to 1, and all other elements are 0.

The construction-specific final demand vector is then calculated as:

$$\mathbf{y}_{\text{constr}} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{y}_{\text{total}} \quad (\text{S3})$$

This vector $\mathbf{y}_{\text{constr}}$ contains zeros for all sectors and regions except for the construction sector final demand in the 23 MENA economies, and is used in Equation (2) of the main text to compute construction-specific embodied emissions.

S2. Database Justification and Mapping Procedures

S2.1 Comparative Analysis of MRIO Databases

We conducted a systematic evaluation of four major MRIO databases— Eora26 (Lenzen et al., 2013), EXIOBASE 3 (Stadler and et al., 2018), GTAP 10 (Aguiar et al., 2019), and WIOD 2016 (Timmer et al., 2015)—to justify our selection of Eora26. Table S1 summarizes the comparative analysis.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of MRIO Databases for MENA Region Coverage

Database	Temporal Coverage	Cov-	Sectoral Res-olution	MENA Regional Resolution (Our 23 Economies)
Eora26	2000–2021		26 sectors	All 23 as individual countries
EXIOBASE 3	1995–2019		163 sectors	7 individual countries; rest aggregated into regional blocks
GTAP 10	2004, 2007, 2011 2014, 2017		65 sectors	18 individual countries; 5 aggregated
WIOD 2016	2000–2014		56 sectors	4 individual countries; 19 not individually represented

Eora26 was selected based on four key criteria:

1. **Country Coverage:** Disaggregated data for all 23 MENA economies versus aggregation in alternatives

2. **Temporal Continuity:** Annual data 2000–2021 covering major construction booms and conflicts
3. **Methodological Consistency:** Harmonized environmental extensions across all years
4. **Proven Applications:** Extensive use in environmental footprint studies (Akizu-Gardoki et al., 2018; Mangır and Şahin, 2022)

S2.2 EDGAR to Eora26 and IEA Fuel-by-Sector Mapping

The mapping of environmental extensions from the source databases (EDGAR for IPPU, IEA × IPCC for energy combustion) to the Eora26 sectoral classification was performed using a cross-walk table. Table S2 provides representative examples of this mapping:

Table 2: Representative Examples of EDGAR to Eora26 Sector Mapping

EDGAR tor/Process	Sec-	IEA Fuel Category	Eora26 Sector
Iron and Steel (ISIC 241)		Coking coal, Blast furnace gas	Other Mining & Basic Metals
Non-ferrous metals (ISIC 242)		–	Other Mining & Basic Metals
Cement production		Petroleum coke, Natural gas	Other Mining & Basic Metals
Road transportation		Motor gasoline, Diesel oil	Transport
Air transportation		Aviation gasoline, Jet fuel	Transport
Residential combustion		Fuelwood, LPG	Other Services

The complete mapping follows Eora26’s official sector definitions and ensures comprehensive coverage of both energy combustion and industrial process emissions. For energy emissions, IEA fuel consumption data was allocated to Eora26 sectors using technology-specific mapping protocols. Industrial process emissions from EDGAR were directly mapped based on ISIC rev. 4 correspondence tables. The complete cross-walk table is available as a separate CSV file upon request.

S3. Data Treatment and Uncertainty Analysis

S3.1 Data Imputation and Sensitivity Analysis for Sudan

Sudan’s emissions data for 2000–2007 were unavailable due to reporting gaps in the source inventories. We implemented a linear interpolation procedure:

$$E_{\text{year}} = E_{2000} + \frac{(E_{2008} - E_{2000})}{(2008 - 2000)} \times (\text{year} - 2000) \quad \text{for year} = 2001 \text{ to } 2007 \quad (\text{S4})$$

where E_{2000} was estimated based on the average growth rate observed in comparable economies during the same period, and E_{2008} is the first available reported value.

A sensitivity analysis testing three alternative imputation methods confirmed that data gaps have negligible impact on MENA-wide results:

Table 3: Sensitivity Analysis of Sudan Data Imputation Methods

Imputation Method	MENA Total 2005 (Mt CO₂)	Deviation from Primary Method
Linear Interpolation (Primary)	287.4	–
Carry-Forward (2008 value)	287.1	-0.10%
Regional Average Growth	287.6	+0.07%
Exclude Sudan	283.7	-1.29%

Given Sudan’s minor contribution to regional totals (¡1.3% across all years), the choice of imputation method has minimal effect on aggregate results.

S3.2 Monte Carlo Uncertainty Quantification

The Monte Carlo analysis incorporated uncertainty components with distributions and parameters aligned with the main text specification:

Table 4: Uncertainty Parameters for Monte Carlo Simulations

Uncertainty Source	Distribution	Parameters	Main Text Reference
Combustion EFs	Normal	$\sigma = 0.15$ (15%)	Section 2.3.4: ±15%
IPPU/Process EFs	Normal	$\sigma = 0.20$ (20%)	Section 2.3.4: ±20%
Trade/Balancing	Normal	$\sigma = 0.05$ (5%)	Section 2.3.4: ±5%
Leontief Inverse	Normal	$\sigma = 0.03$ (3%)	Numerical stability

The combined uncertainty propagation follows:

$$E_{\text{sim}} = E_{\text{base}} \times (1 + \delta_{\text{comb}}) \times (1 + \delta_{\text{ippu}}) \times (1 + \delta_{\text{trade}}) \times (1 + \delta_{\text{leontief}}) \quad (\text{S5})$$

where δ represents random variates from the specified normal distributions. The analysis was conducted with $n = 10,000$ iterations, with results reported as 95% confidence intervals in the main text.

S3.3 Threshold Sensitivity Analysis for Trading Partners

We tested multiple thresholds for identifying meaningful trading partners in the bilateral flow analysis:

Table 5: Threshold Sensitivity Analysis Results for Trading Partner Identification

Threshold	Median Partners	Mean Partners	Import Coverage	Assessment
0.1%	38.0	41.8	97.8%	Overly inclusive
0.3%	22.0	20.6	94.5%	Moderately inclusive
0.5%	13.0	13.7	91.9%	Optimal balance
0.7%	11.0	10.5	90.1%	Moderately exclusive
1.0%	7.0	7.9	87.5%	Overly exclusive

The 0.5% threshold was selected as optimal, capturing 91.9% of embodied emissions while filtering statistical noise from minor trading partners. This threshold ensures robust identification of significant supply chain linkages without excessive aggregation.

S3.4 Emission Intensity Calculation Protocol

Sectoral emission intensities were calculated through a multi-step harmonization process:

1. **Energy Combustion Emissions:** IEA data mapped to Eora26 sectors using cross-walking tables with IPCC Tier 1 emission factors
2. **Industrial Processes:** EDGAR v8.0 data integrated for non-combustion emissions (cement, chemicals, metals)
3. **Emission Factors:** Technology-specific IPCC values applied where available, otherwise regional defaults
4. **Monetary Conversion:** All values converted to constant 2015 USD using World Bank GDP deflators
5. **Intensity Calculation:** $f_i = \text{CO}_{2,i}^{\text{dir}}/x_i$ for each sector i

The complete mapping tables and conversion factors are documented in the cross-walk files available upon request.

S4. Study Country List and Classification

Table 6: Comprehensive List of 23 MENA Economies in Study Scope

ISO3 Code	Country Name	Regional Group	Notes
DZA	Algeria	Maghreb	
BHR	Bahrain	GCC	
DJI	Djibouti	Other	
EGY	Egypt	Mashriq	
IRN	Iran	Mashriq	
IRQ	Iraq	Mashriq	Conflict-affected periods
ISR	Israel	Mashriq	
JOR	Jordan	Mashriq	
KWT	Kuwait	GCC	
LBN	Lebanon	Mashriq	
LBY	Libya	Maghreb	Conflict-affected periods
MAR	Morocco	Maghreb	
MRT	Mauritania	Other	
OMN	Oman	GCC	
PSE	Palestine	Mashriq	
QAT	Qatar	GCC	
SAU	Saudi Arabia	GCC	
SDN	Sudan	Other	Data imputation 2000–2007
SYR	Syria	Mashriq	Conflict-affected periods
TUN	Tunisia	Maghreb	
TUR	Turkey	Other	Transcontinental, strong MENA ties
ARE	United Arab Emirates	GCC	
YEM	Yemen	Other	Conflict-affected periods

S5. Supplemental Figures

Fig. S1: Sectoral composition of embodied CO₂ emissions in MENA construction (2000–2021).

References

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